

The Discounts, Free Shipping, Trust and Consumer Assessment Ratings on Product Purchasing Decisions on The Shopee Application

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Abstract

E-commerce Shopee is one of the E-commerce in Indonesia which has a positive trend as the leader of the Indonesian marketplace. This study aims to determine how much influence discounts, free shipping, trust and consumer assessment ratings have on purchasing decisions for cosmetic products on Shopee application users by taking the research subject of the Labuhanbatu Regency community. The research method used is quantitative research and the data collection method used in this study is by distributing questionnaires in which there are questionnaires distributed to respondents. The sample in this study amounted to 150 respondents who used the shopee application with a distribution period of 3 months. The sampling technique used purposive sampling and data analysis techniques smartPLS 4.0 software model. The findings that respondents who buy or shop at E-commerce Shopee are respondents who have high motivation due to the age and education of respondents who are good enough to have experience shopping online at E-commerce Shopee. The results of hypothesis testing show that the variables of discounts, free shipping, trust and consumer assessment ratings are able to directly influence consumer decisions to shop at E-commerce Shopee.

INTRODUCTION

Purchasing behavior by consumers in E-commerce in Indonesia and around the world continues to increase and the products sought vary from fashion, health, beauty, household appliances, electronics and various others. This phenomenon has become our common concern that there has been a shift or there is a new habitat for consumers to find or buy products more easily and efficiently through E-commerce. (Machová et al., 2022). All E-commerce activities are supported because the development of information technology and technology is able to compete with the dynamics of business systems that were traditional now become more modern. (Shahriari et al., 2015). Information and communication technology without the internet wireless network will also not produce anything including E-commerce itself depends on the internet network in launching promotion and marketing. (Santos et al., 2022).. Another factor that causes this shift is because the presence of Smartphones and their high penetration can make it easier for anyone to interact in cyberspace without limits, including shopping in E-commerce. (Ward et al., 2017).

According to the source (Fokina, 2024) that the number and value of online sales continues to increase. In fact, by 2024, global E-commerce sales will likely surpass \$7 trillion in value. This growth is driven by a number of factors, including the rise of mobile shopping, the growth of social media, and the increasing popularity of subscription services.

Figure 1. Top 10 E-commerce Ranking Countries, 2022

The above data shows that countries in the Asia Pacific and South America region are currently witnessing the fastest growth in the E-commerce sector. This is due to the dynamic adaptation of new technologies as well as the demographic structure of these countries there are more young people than older citizens. These new generations are more tech-savvy and tend to purchase goods online rather than offline. However, the purpose of this research is not to explore the new habitat of consumers, information and communication technology factors, the role of the internet or Smartphone penetration, which have been studied by many academics and professionals. Instead, the author analyzes the factors that E-commerce has as a marketing weapon or the strength of the E-commerce.

The first factor of E-commerce sales is discounts as according to (Lv et al., 2020) that E-commerce businesses should work together, implement reasonable prices, and improve their quality to create a green and healthy shopping environment, to benefit and sustainable development. On the other hand, the second factor of E-commerce sales is free shipping, this is supported by the study results (Yendola & Windasari, 2023) the results of the study clearly illustrate that this type of free shipping with hedonic products will lead to more consumer hedonic motivation. At the same time, the minimum threshold of free shipping will also encourage when combined with utilitarian products. According to (Chung & Yu, 2021) trust is a fundamental pillar of e-commerce on which the digital society and economy

rely heavily in order to function properly. Finally, the factor that is currently trending in E-commerce is the rating of consumer assessments or reviews after shopping online, helping to increase E-commerce sales. (Ullal et al., 2021).

From the analysis of the literature review that is relevant to the research objectives, the authors determine the main research objective is to find out the role of discounts, free shipping, trust and product assessment ratings in influencing purchasing decisions. The importance of writing to set research objectives as well as to limit the scope of the research so that researchers can focus on revealing the phenomenon under study. The findings expected from this study are that the authors can present various important information about E-commerce businesses, especially in Indonesia, which are useful and have an impact on the development of digital marketing science in Indonesia and see changes in consumer behavior in an online business period.

Based on these reasons, the author determines one of the E-commerce in Indonesia which has a positive trend as the leader of the Indonesian marketplace, namely E-commerce Shopee. This is corroborated by (Putri & Zakaria, 2020) that Shopee is the largest E-commerce in Indonesia according to website & social media performance. Therefore, researchers are motivated to examine and test how influential discounts, free shipping, trust and consumer assessment ratings are on purchasing decisions for cosmetic products for Shopee application users.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Discount

At this time online shopping is in great demand and is favored by many people because of the many promos offered by sellers in the shopee application, one of which is discounts, which according to (Brenda et al., 2022) discounts are savings offered by sellers to consumers from the normal price of a product. In line with this according to (Ayu, Sisi Oktaviani Diah Ayu Eka Lestari & Abdul Yusuf: 2021) states that discounts are discounts given by sellers to buyers as a reward for certain activities of the buyer. According to (Rahayu, 2019) stated that discounts can attract buying interest in buyers as consumers, the amount of discounts attracts the attention of consumers, attractive discount offers are an attraction for consumers, so discounts attract consumers to buy certain products. This also agrees with the opinion of (Setyagustina et al., 2022) where discounts are discounts given by sellers so that buyers are interested in buying the discounted product. Based on the opinions of the experts above, it can be concluded that discounting is a technique used by sellers to attract consumers to buy certain products by providing discounts on certain products. The indicators of discounts according to (Baskara 2008); (Razali et al., 2022) namely the amount of the discount, the discount period, the variant of the product that gets the discount.

Free Shipping

Not only discounts are promoted but there is also free shipping that can attract buyers to shop. Where according to (Anggraeni et al., 2023) free shipping is a marketing strategy used by sellers in the market place to attract customers to shop

online without paying shipping costs. According to (Siregar, 2022) free shipping can be interpreted as shipping costs being waived for buyers, so that buyers do not need to add more costs for shipping goods. According to (Wati, 2023) free shipping promos are part of sales promotion to attract consumer buying interest to increase the number of purchases. Free shipping here is free shipping as a promo offered by online business managers to attract buyers. According to (Ermansyah, 2023) this promo is very effective in increasing business sales. Usually, online sales will join a market place that offers free shipping. From the explanation above, it can be concluded that the free shipping strategy has a positive impact on attracting customers, increasing buying interest, and is effective in increasing online business sales, especially when involved in cooperation with marketplaces that support these promotions. The indicators of free shipping according to (Sari 2019); (Razali et al., 2022) namely: free shipping provides attention, free shipping provides interest, free shipping generates desire and free shipping encourages action.

Trust

Trust is a very important variable because trust is what makes customers make purchases. This is in accordance with the opinion (Muttaqin & Amri Rasyid, 2021) trust is when consumers trust a company, they will be more likely to make repeat purchases and share valuable personal information with the company. The above opinion is corroborated by the statement (Gultom et al., 2020) defines trust as the willingness of an individual to rely on other parties involved in the exchange. Consumer trust is trust in products and services (Izzah et al., 2022). Thus, it can be concluded that consumer trust has a significant impact on purchasing decisions, and this is not only related to trust in the product or service, but also includes trust in the company as a whole. The indicators of trust are: trust because it is as expected, trust because it matches the description and trust in getting compensation.

Consumer Assessment Rating

Rating assessment is very influential on consumer purchasing decisions because the rating is a measure of the good and bad quality of a product. This is in accordance with the opinion (Simamora & Islami, 2023) which explains that rating ratings are an important feature that becomes a reference for consumers in assessing the quality of products recommended by someone. According to (Sianipar & Yoestini, 2021) rating can be interpreted as an assessment of users on a product against their experience which refers to the psychological and emotional state they live in when interacting with virtual products in a mediated environment. Rating is a predetermined scale given by consumers which is the same as a review, but a review is in the form of an opinion. The star symbol is used as a rating by online stores, it is said to be good if it has a large number of stars.(Putri, Yayang Giana., 2022). Based on expert opinion, it can be concluded that consumer assessment ratings or it can be said that the form of star symbols in e-commerce has an important role in helping consumers evaluate product quality. Rating ratings can influence consumer preferences and become an important guide in making online purchasing decisions. The indicators of consumer assessment ratings are: providing benefits, making it

easier to choose, creating a sense of trust and deciding on purchases based on the number of assessment ratings.

Purchase Decision

Understanding consumer purchasing decisions has become one of the focuses of this research, where according to (Putra et al., 2016) defines that purchasing decisions are consumer assessments of product alternatives, regarding the determination of preferred brand choices based on certain considerations. According to (Widjanarko et al., 2023) Purchasing decisions are decisions made by consumers which are influenced by financial economic factors, politics, technology, price, culture, and product types. According to (Ayu, Sisi Oktaviani Diah Ayu Eka Lestari & Abdul Yusuf: 2021) The purchase decision is to buy a brand of the most preferred product, there are two factors that can influence, namely coming from purchase intentions and purchase decisions. The first factor is the attitude of others. The second factor is unexpected situational factors. Consumers form purchase intentions based on factors such as expected income. Based on quotes from several authors, it can be concluded that consumer purchasing decisions are the result of an assessment of various product alternatives, influenced by economic, social, and situational factors. Purchase intentions play an important role in shaping the final decision, and factors such as the attitudes of others and unexpected situations can also influence the dynamics of purchasing decisions. The indicators of purchasing decisions are: the stability of product information, deciding to buy because of a preferred brand, buying because it suits your wants and needs, and buying because you get recommendations from others.

Framework and Hypothesis

To make it easier to understand the research, a framework for thinking about the relationship between the independent variables (discounts, free shipping, trust and consumer assessment ratings) and the dependent variable (purchasing decisions) is drawn in the research model as follows:

Figure 2. Thinking Framework

Based on the above framework, the authors formulate the research hypothesis as follows:

1. H₁: Discounts have a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions for cosmetic products for Shopee application users.
2. H₂: Free shipping has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions. cosmetic products on Shopee application users.
3. H₃: Trust has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions. cosmetic products on Shopee application users.
4. H₄: Consumer assessment ratings have a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions for cosmetic products for Shopee application users.

METHOD

This study uses a quantitative research design and uses a *Systematic Literature Review* (SLR) to obtain strong information in supporting the research phenomenon and the theories chosen in this study. The subjects in this study were consumers who had used the Shopee E-commerce application who were domiciled in Labuhanbatu Regency. In connection with the data analysis technique using SmartPLS, the population determination in this study used *Maximum Likelihood Estimation* (MLE), where the sample size was 150 respondents with the right sampling technique using *Purposive Sampling* which will help researchers to set the criteria for having and having experience shopping online. The data analysis used in this study is to use the SmartPLS 4.0 model analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Description

This study took a sample of shopee application users who shop for cosmetic products who live in Pelabuhanbatu. The following will show the respondent's data which is expressed in the form of a diagram of the respondent's identity as follows:

Based on the diagram above, it is known that of the 150 respondents, it shows that based on the gender of the respondents, it is dominated by women, based on the age of the respondents, it is dominated by 21-25 years old and based on the last

level of education, the respondents have a high school education. This means that the identity of the respondents in this study is a sample with criteria that match the wishes of the researcher.

Data Processing Results

Outer Model

In determining the outer model, there are three criteria, including Convergent Validity, Discriminant Validity and Composite Reliability. Therefore, the following is a description of the outer model:

Convergent Validity

The measurement model on Convergent Validity is to see the value of the outer loadings of each indicator of the research instrument. The following is the Outer Loading table:

Table 2. Outer Loadings

Variable Indicators	Discount (X) ₁	Free shipping (X) ₂	Trust (X) ₃	Purchase Decision (Y)	Consumer Assessment Rating (X) ₄
Amount of discount	0,812				
Time period	0,851				
Product variant price	0,755				
Attention		0,843			
Interest		0,710			
Arouse desire		0,816			
Encourage action		0,801			
As expected			0,878		
In accordance with the description			0,839		
Compensation			0,763		
Stability of product information				0,775	
Deciding to buy because of the brand				0,789	
In accordance with wants and needs				0,793	
Other people's recommendations				0,762	
Provides benefits					0,730
Make it easy to choose					0,841
Creating a sense of trust					0,875
Number of assessment ratings					0,855

Source: SmartPLS Program Output Version 4.0

Based on the table above, each indicator has a loading factor > 0.70, so all indicators are valid indicators to measure their constructs.

Discriminant Validity and Composite Reliability

The measurement model on Discriminant Validity and Composite Reliability is to see the value of Cronbach's alpha must be above > 0.70, the composite reliability value is above > 0.60 and the average variance extracted (AVE) value is above > 0.50. The following is a table of construct reliability and validity values:

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

Variables	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Discount (X) ₁	0,732	0,735	0,651
Free Shipping (X) ₂	0,805	0,819	0,631
Trust (X) ₃	0,770	0,773	0,686
Consumer Assessment Rating (X) ₄	0,847	0,874	0,684
Purchase Decision (Y)	0,787	0,794	0,608

Source: SmartPLS Program Output Version 4.0

Based on the table above, it shows that the Cronbach's alpha value of the Discount, Free Shipping, Trust, Consumer Rating Rating and Purchasing Decisions variables has a value greater than 0.70, it can be said that all variables have a high level of reliability. It can be seen based on the table above that the Composite reliability value of each variable has a value greater than 0.60, it can be said that all variables have a high level of reliability. In the table above, the Average variance extracted (AVE) value of the variables Discount, Free Shipping, Trust, Consumer Rating Rating and Purchasing Decisions has a value greater than 0.50, it can be said that all variables in this study have high and good construct validity.

Inner Model

Inner model testing is carried out to see the relationship between constructs, by looking at the R-Square value. Based on data processing that has been carried out using the Smart PLS4.0 program, the R-Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 4. R-Square

Variables	R-square
Purchase Decision (Y)	0,530

Source: SmartPLS Program Output Version 4.0

Based on the table above, it shows that the R-Square value for the purchasing decision variable is 0.530. This acquisition means that the percentage of purchasing

decisions is 53%. This means that the variables of discounts, free shipping, trust and consumer assessment ratings affect purchasing decisions by 53%.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing in this study was carried out by looking at the T-Statistic and P-Values. The hypothesis is said to be accepted if the T-Statistic value > 1.96 and the P-Value value < 0.05 . The following are the results of Path Coefficients:

Table 5. Path Coefficients

Variables	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Discount (X_1) -> Purchase Decision (Y)	0,158	0,164	0,079	2,003	0,045
Free Shipping (X_2) -> Purchase Decision (Y)	0,197	0,199	0,083	2,364	0,018
Trust (X_3) -> Purchase Decision (Y)	0,182	0,192	0,072	2,514	0,012
Consumer Rating (X_4) -> Purchase Decision (Y)	0,390	0,382	0,091	4,261	0,000

Source: SmartPLS Program Output Version 4.0

Based on the table above, it shows that the four hypotheses in this study are accepted or valid because the T-Statistics value > 1.96 and the P-Value value < 0.50 .

Discussion

The Effect of Discounts on Purchasing Decisions

Based on the research results through testing the first hypothesis (H_1), a value of 0.045 was found, indicating that discounts have a positive influence on purchasing decisions for cosmetic products. From testing this hypothesis, of course, the results of this study indicate that discounts are a strong variable that determines purchasing decisions, this is because a discount on a product will create a sense of interest and desire in consumers to make purchases. This is reinforced by research (Riska et al., 2022) which says that a discount on a product will increase consumer buying interest in the product, which leads to an increase in the number of items purchased by consumers. So the greater the discount on a cosmetic product, the more consumer buying interest in the cosmetic product will increase. So these findings are consistent with previous research conducted by (Melfaliza and Nizma, 2022) which states that discounts have a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions. Thus, the results of this study confirm that providing discounts can be an effective strategy in increasing consumer purchasing decisions for cosmetic products.

The Effect of Free Shipping on Purchasing Decisions

Based on the research results through testing the second hypothesis (H_2), a value of 0.018 was found, indicating that the existence of free shipping offers has a

positive influence on purchasing decisions for cosmetic products. From testing this hypothesis, of course, the results of this study state that free shipping is a strong variable that also determines purchasing decisions. In this study, free shipping attracts the attention, interest and desire of consumers to decide to make a purchase. This is because most consumers hesitate to shop online because in addition to paying for the product purchased, consumers also have to pay for shipping costs, so with this free shipping, consumers no longer need to pay shipping costs. This is reinforced by research (Shoffi'ul et al., 2019) which says that free shipping affects purchasing decisions because it is more cost-effective, time-saving and does not need to make purchases online. So these findings are consistent with previous research conducted (Razali et al., 2022) which concluded that free shipping has a significant influence on consumer purchasing decisions. Thus, the results of this study confirm that the free shipping strategy is important in increasing consumer purchasing decisions on cosmetic products.

The Effect of Trust on Purchasing Decisions

Based on the research results through testing the third hypothesis (H_3), a value of 0.012 was found, indicating that trust has a positive influence on purchasing decisions for cosmetic products. From this hypothesis testing, of course, the results of this study state that trust is a strong variable that also determines purchasing decisions. In this study, trust is not only in products and services but also the company as a whole. This is reinforced by the opinion (Sobandi & Somantri, 2020) which states that if consumers have more confidence in the product, service and company, the decision to purchase a product will also increase. With trust, it will have an impact on the consumer's point of view to make repeat purchases of cosmetic products in the Shopee application. The percentage values of the trust indicators that have been carried out in this study show positive and significant. So the findings are consistent with previous research conducted by (Sobandi & Somantri, 2020) which states that trust has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions. Thus, the results of this study confirm that trust plays an important role in shaping consumer purchasing decisions for cosmetic products.

The Effect of Consumer Rating Ratings on Purchasing Decisions

Based on the research results through testing the fourth hypothesis (H_4), a value of 0.00 was found, indicating that consumer assessment ratings have a positive influence on purchasing decisions for cosmetic products. From testing this hypothesis, of course, the results of this study state that consumer assessment ratings are a very strong variable in determining purchasing decisions. In this study, the assessment rating greatly influences purchasing decisions because the consumer assessment rating becomes the benchmark for consumers in seeing the good and bad of a product. This is reinforced by the opinion of (Istiqomah & Marlina, 2020) which says that the higher the assessment rating given by consumers, the better the quality of a product, on the contrary, the less the assessment rating given by consumers, the worse the quality of a product. Thus, the consumer assessment rating is an important guide in making purchasing decisions on a product. This finding is

consistent with previous research conducted by (Sianipar & Yoestini, 2021) which states that *online customer ratings have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions.*

CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this study is the finding that respondents who buy or shop at E-commerce Shopee are respondents who have high motivation due to the age and education of respondents who are good enough to have experience shopping online at E-commerce Shopee. The results of hypothesis testing show that the variables of discounts, free shipping, trust and consumer assessment ratings are able to directly influence consumer decisions to shop at E-commerce Shopee. Through the results of this study, it provides information that E-commerce Shopee is the most active E-commerce in implementing online marketing by prioritizing discounts, free shipping, trust and consumer assessment ratings in Indonesia.

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